

FACTORS DETERMINING MUSEUM EDUCATION*Seyidova Z.**Nakhchivan State University***Abstract**

The purpose of our research is to emphasize the place and importance of "museum education" within the "constructivist education" system, which has been applied since the 2005-2006 academic year. In this context, the concept of "museum" was first examined and the role of the museum in society, the importance of changing and modernizing the concept of museology was emphasized.

Many examples in the world education system show that great importance is attached to museum and school cooperation. Many educational levels offer courses on "museum education", both at the bachelor's and at other levels. While highlighting some gaps in education, our research highlights the role of museums in uncovering talents and skills that cannot be identified in the educational environment and the possible lasting learning processes of encountering real objects.

Keywords: Education, constructivist education, museums, museum education.

1. Introduction

A museum, in its simplest definition: a building designed and organized to display collections of objects for analysis, research and enjoyment (Allan, 1963). However, within the framework of modern museology, the concept of "museum" should be defined from a broader perspective. As it is known, "Respect for the past values of a society can be measured by preserving its artistic and cultural heritage. A society that cannot protect its past cannot survive in the future. Therefore, museums are important institutions that create historical awareness in society, and therefore keeping the connection with society alive is part of the concept of modern museology" (Abacı, 1996).

On the other hand, a comprehensive and important definition was given by ICOM (International Council of Museums) regarding our research topic: "A museum is not only for profit, but serves society and its development, is open to the public, and conducts research on materials that bear witness to people and their environment, it is an institution that collects them, protects them, shares information, and finally exhibits them for purposes such as exams, education, entertainment, and preserves continuity. (McLean, 1996)

As Meric (2003) points out, museums are display sites of social memory through content, collection and often spatial location. "Visual elements" presented according to historical information indirectly and sometimes directly contribute to the formation of historical consciousness, help to add new meanings to this consciousness, and play an important role in the creation of public memory. In this sense, it can easily be said that museums are indispensable institutions, especially for newly founded nations, in terms of transferring the material evidence of the past to the future. Undoubtedly, museology and, therefore, the concept of museums play an extremely important role in the structuring of societies and the formation of social identity.

From the past to the present, the culture of visiting museums, which is generally closer to the cultural and educated strata of society, has unfortunately not developed so much in the segment of society consisting of low-income and less educated people. For museums that consider approaching the public in accordance with the concept of modern museology, covering every layer

of the society; The main task has been to ensure that people of all income and education levels come to museums. Museums today strive to achieve this by organizing many interesting exhibitions, educational programs and events to ensure the participation of all sections of society. The various programs and temporary exhibitions are designed to educate the community and have a good time in the process. One of the goals is that a person who comes to the museum not only gets information, but also has a good time, feels happy and comfortable, and for these reasons repeats the visit to the museum often (Atagök, 1999). The museum is in constant cultural contact with the public as an institution that preserves and presents the tangible and intangible cultural heritage of the society. For this reason, museums should be close to society and attract people's attention (Atik, 1999).

But apart from all this the important thing to mention; In the context of a naturally developing and changing society and the "new education" approach, museums now have a role to play more than strengthening connections with the past or making people love art. The face of museology has changed with the transition from the static spatial concept of classical museology, which looks at society from a distance, to the concept of living modern museology, which uses new presentation and expression methods and is built as a cultural unit.

2. The importance of museum education within constructivist education

According to today's thinking, life itself is already a school and learning never ends. The Socratic constructivist approach is the most popular and practiced educational philosophy today.

As we mentioned earlier, museums; In particular, they are the institutions of communication and information transmission that transmit the scientific and cultural collection of a nation, human history in general, to future generations, and show the place of a person's social identity and culture within the universal culture and values. Although museums have primary information that stimulates the mind, there is generally informal, spontaneous education based on observation, where learning happens without realizing it.

In this context, as research scientist Atağök stated: If education is the transmission of knowledge, then the works and objects in museum collections transmit knowledge by their presence. If education is about developing knowledge, thinking, and comparing, museums can teach accurate observation, monitoring, and logical continuity and comparison by showing connections between objects that books and lectures can't make clear. If education is to develop creativity and thinking, museums not only awaken a sense of appreciation by showing the best examples of the works in their collections, but also create a source of enthusiasm for creativity (Atağök, 1994).

The task of a qualified teacher, which comes to the fore in constructivist education, is to build the experience for a specific purpose. The main principle here is that education should be student-centered, that is, it should be based on students' experiences (Yapıcı, 2007; Saban, 2002).

As the famous philosopher Giambattista Vico, one of the theorists of constructivist education, said, people can clearly understand what they live through their experiences (Hawkins, 1994). For this reason, the student is required to be active in constructivist education. Being active can be achieved by thinking about the current issue. In order for a person to think about the topic being discussed, it should be clear what that topic is. This approach will be beneficial in providing a real-life environment and understanding the learning in context. (Jonassen, 2003) In the light of all this, it is possible to understand how appropriate, necessary and important it is to use museums as an 'active learning' environment within the framework of constructivist education accepted in our country.

3. Overview of Museum Education in the World

Thanks to the Museum Pedagogical Center (MPZ), which was established in Germany in 1973, various educational programs, museum tours, play activities and publications are carried out both in historical castles and in 14 different museums. Attention is paid to the parallelization of special programs developed on the computer with school programs, guided tours, information, discussions and exercises are organized for all students of different school ages on set dates. The German Center for Museum Pedagogy runs its programs in conjunction with school programs, and each school's program includes museum visits at least twice a year (Abacı, 1996).

In England, we see that the idea of a "travel museum" has been implemented since 1884. In addition, Haslemere Museum, the first educational museum in England, was opened in 1894-1895. The New Castle Faculty of Education opened a course in 1980 called "Using Museums and Museum Artifacts as Educational Tools". On the other hand, the Institute of Education of the University of London has added an elective course on "Museums, Galleries, Schools" to its graduate certificate. In addition, North Worcestershire College has launched a one-year postgraduate diploma program in Museums in Education.

Although the USA has a relatively young history compared to European countries in this regard, it has

not failed to provide educational qualities to museums in a short period of time. (Shahan, 2005) Educational programs for students and teachers seem to play a very active role in museums in the United States. These museum activities include organizing courses for teachers and teacher candidates, offering internship opportunities to college and high school students in their workshops and galleries each year, and offering family and children's workshops for preschool groups. (Abacı, 2005). In addition, museum-related courses attract attention in the undergraduate curriculum of Education faculties.

4. Research goals and methods

In this study, the social function of museums and their development throughout history were first evaluated, then examples of museum-school cooperation and the position of museums in education in Europe and America were given. The document analysis technique was used throughout the research, and as a result of the obtained data, it was tried to draw attention to the issue of "museum education", which can be considered as the main gap in the education system.

As it is known, the constructivist educational approach is applied in education in our country. However, teachers are not given detailed training on this topic, and there is a lack of museum education that can become a constructivist educational platform and support many courses. In this regard, the necessity of museum education is mentioned along with examples.

5. Conclusion and proposal

As a result, if we consider that we live in a geography that can be characterized as a mosaic of civilizations from a historical and cultural point of view, we will see that the extremely rich museums of our country are extremely productive educational, historical, artistic, cultural, communicative and active learning environments that can bring teachers and students together.

Activities related to the museum, which can be effectively used in concretizing the lessons and are thought to achieve the effective and active learning targeted by constructivist education, can be achieved if they are carried out by knowledgeable, conscious and trained teachers about the museum. A "Museum Education" course can be created at different stages of our education, where teachers can gain knowledge and experience to effectively prepare and evaluate museums at the educational stage.

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